

A STUDY ON CONSUMER SATISFACTION IN ONLINE SHOPPING WEBSITES

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Abstract: *E-commerce trading goods and services through internet and products with the help of introduced new possibilities in trading E-commerce offers product and services through websites, a customer simply has to visit an Ecommerce website and Browse various offering through browser catalog, a customer can select multiple websits and can add them to cart once the shopping is done the customer can checkout and payment section where various online payment option are available like internet Banking ,credit, debit card an attempt has been made to critically examine the comparison of customer satisfaction of two big E-Retailers. amazon and Flipkart Both these different E-commerce market available in India.*

Key words: Amazon, Customer, E-commerce, Flipkart, Services, E-shopping websites

Introduction

Online shopping is a form of electronic commerce which allows customers to buy goods and services from a seller over the through the internet. Using a web browser or a mobile app, consumer find a product of by visiting the website of the retailer directly or by searching among alternative vendors using a shopping search engine. Which displays the same products availability and pricing at different e-retailers as of 2020 customer can shop online using a range of different computers and devices including desktop computers, laptop, computers and smart phones. Amazon founded by Jeff Bezos in 1994, amazon.com .in is an American multinational technology company Seattle, Washington which focuses on ecommerce digital marketing and artificial intelligence. It is one of the big five companies in the USA information technology industry, along with Google “One of the most influential economic and cultural forces the world” as well as the worlds most valuable brand. Flipkart is an ecommerce company founded in 2007 and graduated from the Delhi Indian institutes of technology both Mr. sachine bansal and bunny bansal. Even before they both they worked for

amazon Flipkart Bangalore Karnataka, head quarters. It is registered and processed in Singapore by a Singapore based company earlier Flipkart was named “Digi flip” but latter an it shopped items own medical and households appliance to “citrin” brand during period Flipkart extending his Services from books to different items like electronic. Online stores usually enable shopper to use search features to find a specific models, brand or items. Online customer must have access to the internet and a valid method of payment in order to Complete a transaction, such as a credit card, an interact enabled debit card, or service such as pay pal .for physical products E-retailer ships the products to customers.

Objectives of the Study

Below following are the objectives of the study

- 1.Analysis the facility provide by the selected online shopping websites
- 2.The know the customer preference between the Amazon and Flipkart

Research Methodology

In this research primary data has been collected through Google forms sample size where 50 respondent take it from Bangalore youths The data has been collected to those user of Amazon and Flipkart. The respond it using e commerce site for purpose of shopping product and services the present study is to underlies the current status of e-commerce company Flipkart and Amazon in Indian market.

Scope of the Study

The present study has been confined to study on consumer buying behaviour towards purchasing used products. The study has been covered only from the customers of preference towards online shopping of used of goods and services.

Review of Literature

Adrita Goswami.al (2013),studied “Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping with Reference to Teenage Group of Jorhat Town” study concludes that online customers are satisfied in the aspects such as Price, Quality of products, Ease of use in mobile platform and Timely Delivery at remote areas. This research explicitly indicates that online marketer should give more importance on price factor and after sale factor.

Devaki V.P.T, Latasri O.T.V, S Camogie (2014), in their paper “Factors Affecting Online shopping of Customers” revealed that the most important factor influencing online shopping is- security, followed by-trust worthy shopping and – website design/features and the lea important factor influencing is – bargaining shopping, there is no significant association

between security and website design/features of the respondents and their overall online buying behaviour and customer satisfaction.

Kanwal Gurleen (2012), "Customers satisfaction towards Online shopping", discussed that different options in internet encouraged people to search and eventually purchase online, because there are more than 100 million internet users in India. People those who are using internet from 5 to 7 hours a day were found to be adopter of online shopping. Price consciousness, convenience and variety, easy payment options and challenges of online shopping are the factors found to be a significant in online shopping

Ashish Pant (2014), "An Online Shopping Change the Traditional Path of Consumer Purchasing" concluded in his research article that a successful web store is not the just a good looking website with the dynamic technical features but is also emphasis on building the relationship with customers with making money. The success of any e-tailer company in India is depending upon its popularity, its branding image, its unique & fair policies, and its customer

Analysis

Based on the respondent data Insert the table write the interpretation its shows the respondent buying behaviour and customer satisfaction in online shopping websites. it shows the usage of online shopping websites and payment method, level of satisfaction, customer expectation.

Usage of E-commerce online shopping websites

Now a days online shopping websites are many more are their like Amazon, Flipkart, and others many people are using online shopping websites to by the products people are jump to many websites comparing all the websites and by the items now a days every youths are using online

shopping websites not only one websites people are using different websites.

Table:1 Usage of E-commerce online shopping websites

Sl.No	E-commerce online shopping websites	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Amazon	15	30%
2	Flipkart	23	46%
3	Others	12	24%
4	Total	50	100%

From the above Table-1 shows usage of online shopping websites it can interpret the data how offer respondents are doing shopping in online shopping websites table shows the 30% people are using Amazon, 46% people are using Flipkart ,24% people are using other online shopping websites the highest rate usage websites is Flipkart it gets the 46% rate of usage.

E-commerce websites Utilisation

People are using online shopping websites this websites are helps to people in many ways. Like checking the products descriptions, price, colour, and date of delivery the people are using many websites to by the products. take a data from respondents using online shopping websites comfortably are not below Table will shows the result.

Table:2 Utilisations of E-commerce online shopping websites

SL.NO	Utilisation of online shopping websites	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Comfortable	46	92%
2	Not comfortable	04	08%
	Total	50	100%

Table-2 shows the utilization of online shopping websites it can interpret that the how offer

respondents are doing shopping online websites table shows the 98% of people are using comfortable in online shopping application 8% of people are not comfortable using online shopping websites most of people are using comfortable using in online shopping websites.

Customers convenience in payment method

Using online shopping websites to buy the products when we buy the product that time pay the amount through internet or cash on delivery people are scared to pay the amount in online because it is not safe and secure so people choose the cash on delivery. Customers pay the amount according to their convenience below Table shows the which payment methods is highly preferred to Customers and customers preference.

Table:3 Convenience in payment method

SL.NO	Payment methods	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Online payment	15	30%
2	Cash on delivery	35	70%
3	Total	50	100%

Table-3 shows the which payment method is most preferred customers 70% people are preferred cash on delivery remaining 30% people are preferred online payment so most of all people are preferred cash on delivery. According to respondents cash on delivery is safe. Customers comfortable to pay cash to delivery person customer more preferred to pay on cash or cash on delivery its more convenience.

E-commerce provides the best products

E-commerce online shopping websites provides the best products to customers. Customer wants to best products from online shopping websites many websites provides the products to customers like electronics, Apperels, food, like that products are available in Online shopping websites. Customers searching the products by online which websites available best products

below Table shows the data

Table:4 E-commerce online shopping websites provides the best products to customers

SL.NO	Provides the best products	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Amazon	19	38%
2	Flipkart	21	42%
3	Others	10	20%
4	Total	50	100%

From the above Table-4 shows the which websites give the chip and best to customer 38% people get chip and best products from Amazon, 42% people from Flipkart, 20% people get from other websites so chip and best products get from Flipkart according to above the table customers always expect the low price get a quality of products Table-4 shows the flipkart is provides the best products according to respondents.

Highest discount and offer provide online shopping websites to customers

Customer expecting the more offer and discount from online shopping websites when will provides the more offers and discount customer buy the more and more products .online shopping websites provides the more discount to customers it is a logic for attract the more customers. customers wants to more offers and discount like 50%off, buy one get two free like that when will give the more offers and discounts that time online shopping also earn more profit

Online shopping websites given offers to customers seasonally twies like special days gives the offers like dhasara, ugadi, that time will gives the more offers and discounts to customers.

Table:5 Highest discount and offer provides to customers

SL.NO	Provides the highest offers and discounts	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Amazon	25	50%
2	Flipkart	24	48%
3	Others	01	02%
4	Total	50	100%

Customer Searching which websites gives the more discount to customer. according to above table-5 shows that it can interpret the 50% people are choosing Amazon give the more discount to customer 48% people are choosing Flipkart, 2% people are choosing other websites. Over all table saying Amazon gives the more discount to customers

Customer expectations from E-commerce online shopping websites

The customers expectations from online shopping websites are quality of products and low price and time pickup online shopping websites meets the customers needs and expectations bellow Table will shows the what are the things customers expecting from online shopping websites

Table:6 Customer expectations from online shopping websites

SL.NO	Expectations from online shopping websites	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Quality of products	27	54%
2	Chip, low price	18	36%
3	Free shipping	03	06%
4	Nothing	02	04%
5	Total	50	100%

Above Table-6 shows the customer expectation from online shopping websites. 54% people are expecting quality of the product then 36% people are expecting chip price 6% people are expecting free shipping 4% people are expecting offer and discount so over all the table shows the customer expecting more quality of the product.

Satisfactions from online shopping websites to customers

Online shopping websites main goal is customers satisfactions the customer satisfactions is not an easy thing to E-commerce shopping websites it is the main difficulty faced the online shopping websites to satisfactions the customers once customer will satisfied the customer loyal to that online shopping website.

Table :7 Satisfactions from online shopping websites to customers

SL.NO	Satisfactions from online shopping websites	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Amazon	21	46%
2	Flipkart	18	32%
3	Others	11	22%
4	Total	50	100%

Table-7 show the it can interprite which online shopping websites give the more satisfaction to customers 42%people are get satisfied from Amazon .then 36%people are get satisfied from Flipkart 22% people are satisfied from other online shopping websites analysis of over all the table Amazon more satisfaction gives to customer

Over all the experience from e-commerce online shopping websites

Customers will search the products, buy the products, pay the amount through online or cash will pay to after getting the products then giving the feedback to online shopping websites this over all the procedure customers getting good experience or average, poor bellow Table will shows the experience from online shopping websites.

Table :8 Over all the experience from e-commerce online shopping websites

SL.NO	Experience from online shopping websites	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Excellent	12	24%
2	Very good	19	38%
3	Average	15	30%
4	Poor	04	08%
5	Total	50	100%

From the above Table-8 shows the overall the online shopping experience 24% people are telling excellent, 38% of people are telling very good experience,30% of people are telling average ,8% of people are telling poor experience from online shopping websites. Analysis of above table very good experience from online shopping websites is highest percentage data getting from respondents.

Findings

- Female response are showing more interest to do shopping in online compared to male respondents
- Customer are Expecting quality products from E-commerce websites it bit expensive
- 18-25 age group people are using more online shopping websites
- Customer expectations is discount and cheap and best products from E-commerce websites
- Customer preference most cash on delivery method

Suggestions

Customer more satisfaction from the Flipkart performing well but not enough customer expectations is quality of the product and free delivery Amazon and Flipkart increase the product quantity provide the more discount and offers to customers and on time delivery There are so many cases people suffer from parking and free shipping improve the quality of Products and free shipping of products.

Conclusion

The study with over all the work flow of E-commerce online shopping websites playing the very good role in the India, Flipkart and Amazon they are performing well in the competitive markets.

They increases their work networks and reach the ultimate aim and attracting the more customers and reaching the customers needs and wants. Flipkart and amazon creating good brand image in the market Amazon making good packing and time delivered products safe and secure is more important to customers. Flipkart and Amazon doing very well Indian E-commerce market.

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